

2nd INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON RISK ASSESSMENT OF PHARMACEUTICALS IN THE ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT BOOK

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INTRODUCING 'PLAS-MED' MICROPLASTICS AND MICROCONTAMINANTS IN THE MEDITERRANEAN COAST: ENVIRONMENTAL AND HUMAN HEALTH IMPACTS

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The so-called marine litter, and in particular microplastics (MPLs), are recognised by the scientific community as an emerging risk for the environment and human health. The aim of PLAS-MED is to assess the risks associated with MPLs and their ability to accumulate and transfer other microcontaminants to aquatic organisms, including the highly toxic and persistent marine biotoxins and persistent organic compounds (POPs), as well as contaminants of emerging concern (pharmaceuticals, personal care products, pesticides etc).

This project counts with the participation of three research institutes (Institute of Environmental Assessment and Water Research - IDAEA-CSIC, Spanish Institute of Oceanography - IEO and Catalan Institute for Water Research - ICRA) and is organised in the four research modules with specific objectives:

- Evaluation of the presence, fate and impact of microplastics in marine and freshwater systems, taking the Mediterranean coast as a case study. The project monitors the presence of MPLs, POPs and emerging organic contaminants at the Ebro Delta (NE Iberian Peninsula) and at the Mar Menor coastal lagoon (SE Iberian Peninsula).
- Assessment of the potential of adsorption of the organic contaminants to microplastics by means of mesocosms studies (marine and fluvial), in order to determine their contribution in the transference of such contaminants to the aquatic organisms.
- Study of the bioaccumulation, toxicity and metabolic changes in aquatic organisms in response to the exposure to contaminants, as well as the impact that the associated presence of microplastics might have.
- Evaluation of the potential risk for human health through the consumption of fish and seafood exposed to contaminated MPLs, including the effects from food preparation.

Update information of the action can be followed at <https://www.plas-med.es/>

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